

A Study on Surgical Outcome of Transurethral Resection of Prostate and Concomitant Inguinal Hernioplasty in A Tertiary Centre Of Uttar PradeshSomvanshi Vineet Singh¹, Ahmed Shamshad², Garg Vipul³, Dalal Rajesh Kumar⁴¹Associate Professor, Dept. Of General Surgery, Dr BS Kushwah Institute of Medical Sciences, Kanpur²Assistant Professor, Dept. Of General Surgery, Dr BS Kushwah Institute of Medical Sciences, Kanpur³Assistant Professor, Dept. Of Biochemistry, SMS Medical College, Jaipur⁴Senior Resident, Department of Community Medicine, ESIC PGIMS and Medical College and ODC (EZ) Joka Kolkata

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Older man faces benign enlargement of prostate leading to bladder outlet obstruction and difficulty in urination for which more abdominal force is applied. This causes combined presence of inguinal hernia with BPH and operating both in the same sitting may reduce post operative recovery and complications. This research tries to study the same.

Material and Methods: A retrospective study was conducted in Dept. Of General Surgery, Dr BS Kushwah Institute of Medical Sciences, Kanpur from 2018 to 2024 and included 95 those patients who underwent TURP and inguinal hernia repair at the same sitting. Intra-operative and post operative complications were noted. Surgical characteristics such as post operative duration of hospital stay, duration of the surgery, duration of Foleys catheterization, recatheterization, intraoperative and postoperative complications etc were evaluated. This study also tried to know the efficacy of open versus laparoscopic hernioplasty.

Results: Among the 95 cases of combined approach of inguinal hernioplasty and TURP the mean operative time was 3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes with only 3 (3.2%) operative complications and no post operative stay complications. Mean post operative hospital stay was 3.5 \pm 1.0 days, recatheterization was in 11(11.6%) and 11(11.6%) discharged with Folley catheter. The mean operative time, duration of hospital stay, duration Foleys catheterization, analgesic and antibiotic use was significantly lesser ($p < 0.05$) with laparoscopic hernioplasty compared to open hernioplasty.

Conclusion: Surgical outcome of TURP and concomitant inguinal hernioplasty is better in terms of complications, operative and post operative recovery and patient morbidity is concerned. Even the efficacy of laparoscopic hernioplasty, in view of patient morbidity, is found to be better than open hernioplasty. So combined surgery i.e. TURP and hernioplasty specially laparoscopic hernioplasty is a better option than both surgeries done at interval.

Keywords: Laparoscopic hernioplasty, TURP, Surgical outcome, Post Operative complications.

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Introduction

Urinary discomfort is caused by benign prostate enlargement or BPH which compresses the urethra leading to urinary obstruction. BPH causes urinary tract infections, hydronephrosis, bladder stones etc . [1] The Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries and Risk Factors Study (GBD) 2019, which was supported by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, found that the number of instances of these disorders increased by over 70% from 51.1 million in 2000 to 94 million in 2019 . [2] In India prevalence of Benign Prostrate Hyperplasia (BPH) is around 50% of men by the age of 60 years . [1] Therefore, in order to avoid difficulties, the issue of BPH must be treated properly.

Constant increased intra-abdominal pressure in

BPH patients, to help passing urine, triggered by age-related muscle degeneration with time can lead to the formation of hernias. Due to concomitant occurrence , treating benign prostatic hyperplasia and inguinal hernia repair together in a single sitting may be a good way to reduce hospital stays, surgical procedures and patient morbidity. [3] 12%–23% of men receiving prostate surgery had an inguinal hernia, while 12%–25% of patients undergoing hernioplasty have BPH symptoms. [4–6]

Hernia repair surgery causes discomfort at the surgical site, which makes it difficult for patients to transition early from catheterization and may require consideration of catheter reinsertion. Even

TURP itself frequently requires intra-abdominal pressure for postoperative voiding. [7,8] So this study was done with an objective to study the surgical outcome of TURP and concomitant hernioplasty done in a single sitting also to compare the surgical and post operative characteristics of open versus laparoscopic hernioplasty.

Methods

A retrospective study was conducted in Dept. Of General Surgery, Dr BS Kushwah Institute of Medical Sciences, Kanpur from 2018 to 2024 and included 95 those patients who underwent TURP and inguinal hernia repair at the same sitting. Selected patients had ASA score less than 4 and followed up for one year. Those patients with coagulative disorder, malignant pathology and previous history of TURP were excluded.

Proper history regarding age, co-morbidity, earlier abdominal surgical history, history of earlier occurrence of hernia, type of hernia and position of hernia, serum PSA level etc were noted. Type of hernia operation i.e., open, or laparoscopic hernioplasty and type of TURP i.e. by traditional

bipolar TURP or laser prostatectomy were noted. Intra-operative complications, mean operative time, mean duration of catheterization, mean duration of post operative stay, mean PSA level number of patients who were re-catheterized and number of patients who were discharged with catheter were noted. Even number of patients who needed IV/IM antibiotic and analgesic were noted. Post operative complications if any were noted.

All data recorded in Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 16 software was used to analyze data. Quantitative variables were presented in frequency, percentage and mean (SD). Quantitative dependent variable between two groups were analyzed by one-way ANNOVA and qualitative variable analyzed by Chi-square test. A 'p' value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

As per study design and inclusion criteria (including ASA score <4) 95 patients were selected for undergoing TURP and inguinal hernioplasty in one sitting. The table 1 describe the basic clinical characteristics of the patients.

Table 1: Clinical characteristics of the study subjects (N=95)

	Frequency	Percentage
Abdominal surgical history		
No Surgery	68	71.6
Hernioplasty SSS	8	8.4
Hernioplasty CLS	9	9.5
Appendicectomy	4	4.2
Cholecystectomy	5	5.3
Colorectal Surgery	1	1.1
History of Anticoagulant use		
Yes	12	12.6
No	83	87.4
History of earlier occurrence		
Primary	87	91.6
Recurrent	8	8.4
Type of hernia		
Direct	40	42.1
Indirect	34	35.8
Mixed	21	22.1
Position of hernia		
UL Left	26	27.3
UL Right	41	43.2
BL	28	29.5
Total	95	100.0

The mean age of the patients was 72.05 ± 6.36 yrs and according to history of co-morbidity 17 (17.9%) , 37 (38.9%), 9 (9.5%) , 4 (4.2%) and

3(3.2%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension, CAD, Asthma/COPD and CKD respectively.

Only 8(8.4%) patients had recurrent hernia and rest 87 (91.6%) had primary hernia. In this study 8(8.4%) patients had earlier history of same side hernioplasty and 9 (9.5%) had contralateral side hernioplasty. Rest 4(4.2%), 5 (5.3%) and 1(1.1%) had earlier history of appendicectomy, cholecystectomy and colorectal surgery, respectively. In this study 40(42.1%) had direct hernia, 34(35.8%) had indirect hernia and rest

21(22.1%) had mixed hernia. In this study 26(27.3%) had left sided unilateral hernia, 41(43.2%) had right sided unilateral hernia. Rest 28(29.5%) had bilateral hernia. Out of total 95 patients 12 (12.6%) had history of anticoagulants use. The mean prostate volume was 60.5 ± 16.2 ml. The resected prostate specimen was sent for HPE to rule out malignancy. The mean PSA level was 5.6 ± 1.1 nano gm /ml.

Table 2: Intra-operative and post operative surgical characteristics and complications. (N=95)

Type of Hernia Operation	
Open Hernioplasty	58 (61.1%)
Lap Hernioplasty	37 (38.9%)
	16 Three port 21 Single port
Type of TURP	
Bipolar	9 (9.5%)
Laser	86 (90.5%)
Intra-operative complications	
No Complications	92 (96.8%)
Hemorrhage	2 (2.1%)
Spermatic Cord Injury	1 (1.1%)
Mean Operation Time	
	3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes
Mean TURP volume	
	31.3 \pm 6.8 ml
Mean Duration of Folley's Catheterization	
	50.9 \pm 15.9 hr
Recatheterization	
	11 (11.6%)
Patient discharged with folleys'	
	11 (11.6%)
Manual Bladder Irrigation	
	2 (2.1%)
Patients managed by IV/IM analgesic	
	24(25.3%)
Post Operative stay complications	
	0

The intra-operative and post operative surgical characteristics and complications are depicted in the table 2.

In this study the meantime taken for the combined surgery was 3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes.

During operating for hernia as per patient choice and operative criteria 58(61.1%) underwent open hernioplasty and 37(38.9%) underwent laparoscopic hernioplasty with in 16 patients three ports were used and in 21 patients single port was used. Again 9 (9.5%) underwent bipolar TURP and rest 86(90.5%) underwent laser prostatectomy. The average resected prostate volume was 31.3 ± 6.8 ml. Only 2(2.1%) patients developed mild hemorrhage which was managed immediately and 1(1.1%) developed spermatic cord injury which was repaired in the same sitting.

During post operation hospital stay no patient developed port site hemorrhage or infection and even no gross hematuria was there. The mean duration

of folleys catheterization was 50.9 ± 15.9 hr. Recatheterization was done in 11 (11.6%) patients. Manual bladder irrigation was done in 2(2.1%) patients. Post operative 24(25.3%) patients were managed by IV/IM analgesic and IV antibiotics was used in 24 (25.3%) patients. 11 (11.6%) patients were discharged with folleys catheterization. Among the 9 patients who underwent bipolar TURP 2 (22.2%) developed intra-operative complications and among 86 patients who underwent laser prostatectomy 1(1.2%) patient developed post-operative complications and this difference was statistically significant. (0.023)

Comparative findings of surgical characteristics and outcome of patients who underwent open hernioplasty and laparoscopic hernioplasty are depicted in table 3

The average duration of hospital stay was 3.5 ± 1.0 days.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of surgical characteristics and outcome of patients with open and laparoscopic hernioplasty. (N= 95)

	Open Hernioplasty	Laparoscopic Hernioplasty	p
Total Number of Patients	58	37	
Mean Age (yrs)	71.2±5.8	73.4±6.7	0.086
Mean Prostate Volume (ml)	62.2±15.9	58±16.6	0.224
Mean Prostate Resection Volume (ml)	30.9±7.1	31.9±6.2	0.503
Mean Operation Time	3hr50min±53min	3hr±36min	0.000
Mean Duration of Stay	3.83±1.04 days	2.99±0.78 days	0.000
Mean Duration of Foleys	56.26±15.33hr	42.65±13.19 hr	0.000
Means PSA Level (nano gm/ml)	5.04±1.15	6.4±0.03	0.000
IV/IM Analgesic Use	22(23.2%)	2 (2.1%)	0.000
Re-catheterization	9 (9.5%)	2 (2.1%)	0.133
IV Antibiotic Use	22 (23.2%)	2 (2.1%)	0.000
Intra Operative Complications	2 (2.1%)	1 (1.1%)	0.839

In this study out of total 95 patients 58 underwent open hernioplasty and 37 underwent laparoscopic hernioplasty along with TURP in a single sitting. The mean age of open hernioplasty group was 71.2±5.8 yrs and for laparoscopic hernioplasty group was 73.4±6.7 and this difference was not statistically significant. (p=0.086). Similarly, the mean prostate volume was 62.2±15.9 ml and 58±16.6 ml respectively and this difference was also not statistically significant (p=0.224). Similarly, the mean over all prostatic resection volume was 31.3±6.7 ml and that of the above two group was 30.9±7.1 ml and 31.9±6.2 ml respectively (p=0.503)

The mean operation time for the open hernioplasty group was 3hr50min±53min and for laparoscopic hernioplasty group was significantly lesser i.e. 3hr±36min (p<0.001). Similarly, the mean duration of stay of above two group was 3.83±1.04 days and 2.99±0.78 days respectively and this difference was also statistically significant ((p<0.001) i.e. lesser in laparoscopic hernioplasty group. Again, the mean duration of foleys catheterization in open hernioplasty group was 56.26±15.33hr and in laparoscopic hernioplasty group it was significantly lesser i.e., 42.65±13.19 hr (p<0.001). The mean PSA level of the above two groups were 5.04±1.15 nano gm/ml and 6.4±0.03 nano gm/ml respectively and this difference was statistically significant. (p<0.001)

In this study IV/IM analgesic use in open hernioplasty group and laparoscopic hernioplasty group was in 22(23.2%) and 2 (2.1%) respectively and this difference was statistically significant (p<0.001). Similarly, the IV antibiotic use was in 22(23.2%) and 2 (2.1%) respectively and this difference was also statistically significant (p<0.001). It means both IV/IM analgesic and antibiotic requirement was in significant lesser patients in the

laparoscopic hernioplasty group. Re-catheterization was in 9 (9.5%) and 2 (2.1%) respectively and this difference was not statistically significant. (p=0.133). Similarly intra-operative complications were in 2(2.1%) and 1 (1.1%) in the above two group and this difference was not statistically significant. (p=0.839).

Discussion

Inguinal hernia and benign hypertrophy of prostate are common in people of age 50 yrs and older. According to literature they are found in 15% to 25%. The hernia may occur in patients of BPH due to disorders of the lower urinary tract. If both disorder is operated simultaneously in a single stage then satisfactory results can be obtained and it can not only reduce cost of hospital stay but also reduce the multiple risk of anesthesia. [9] So this retrospective study was done on 95 patients who underwent concomitant inguinal hernioplasty and TURP to study the surgical outcome and also to compare the surgical and post operative characteristics of open versus laparoscopic hernioplasty.

In our study mean age of the patients was 72.05 ± 6.36 yrs and 17 (17.9%), 37 (38.9%), 9 (9.5%), 4 (4.2%) and 3(3.2%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension, CAD, Asthma/COPD and CKD respectively. Only 8(8.4%) patients had recurrent hernia. In this study 8(8.4%) patients had earlier history of same side hernioplasty and 9 (9.5%) had contralateral side hernioplasty. 40(42.1%) had direct hernia, 34(35.8%) had indirect hernia and rest 21(22.1%) had mixed hernia. In our study 26(27.4%) had left sided unilateral hernia, 41(43.2%) had right sided unilateral hernia. Rest 28(29.5%) had bilateral hernia. The mean prostate volume found to be 60.5 ± 16.2 ml, and the mean PSA level was 5.6 ± 1.1 nano gm/ml.

In a retrospective study done in Instituto Nacional de la Nutrición in México by Ojeda et al [10] who compared 41 combined inguinal herniorrhaphy and

transurethral prostatectomy(group 1) (from January 1979 and June 1988) with 100 cases of inguinal herniorrhaphy alone (group 2) and 100 consecutive cases of transurethral prostatectomy alone (group 3) and found that rate of operative and post operative complications were not significantly higher between the groups. There was no recurrence of inguinal hernia, post operative hospital stay was comparable and there was no mortality. Even that study added that there was advantage of single anesthetic period, one operative procedure, one hospital stays, and the morbidity and mortality rates were comparable. In our study too there were only 3(3.15%) operative complications, and no post operative complications were there. Only 11 patients were recatheterized and were discharged with catheter.

A RCT was done by Javanmard et al [11] clinics of Shohada Tajrish Hospital, Tehran, Iran, from March 2017 to May 2020 and found that the mean age of the patients in group 1(TURP and mesh herniorrhaphy done in a single operation) was 66.8 ± 5.8 (range 54-81 years and that of group 2 (TURP was done at first, and then, three months later, in another admission, inguinal hernia repair was done) was 65.06 ± 5.8 (range 51-78 years). In our study the mean age was 72.05 ± 6.36 yrs which was a bit on higher side. The mean prostate volume was 38.7 ± 9.3 ml in group I and 37.8 ± 8.3 ml in group II and in this study, it was 60.5 ± 16.2 ml which was on the higher side. In group 1, 15.9% suffered from post operative fever and 6.8% developed wound infection and 11.3% developed UTI (3 month follow up). In group 2, 17.5% developed fever and 20% developed UTI (3 month follow up). In our study only 2(2.1%) patients developed intra operative mild hemorrhage which was managed immediately and 1(1.1%) developed spermatic cord injury which was repaired in the same sitting. In our study no post, operative complications developed. In that study the mean duration of operation in group I and II was 63.04 ± 6.8 minutes and 77.2 ± 8.5 minutes respectively($p < 0.05$). In our study the mean duration of operation was 3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes which is higher compared to that study.

Abarbanel et al [12] on a study on 91 patients on which combined inguinal hernia repair and prostatectomy was done found a low i.e. 4.9% recurrence rate and found no complications. In our study too only, there were 3 intra-operative complications and no post operative complications.

In a study by Dahami et al [13] which included 31 patients with combined surgery of inguinal hernia repair and prostatectomy found favourable outcome in 86% of patients with morbidity rate 10.7%. In our study the operative complications were 3(3.1%) and there were no post operative complications which is similar to that study. The

average hospital stay was 3.6 days which in our study was 3.5 ± 1.0 days which is similar. Only one patient had fever and bleeding on day 1 but in our study, there were no post operative stay complications.

A retrospective study conducted by Barra et al [14] who did a retrospective analysis of 29 patients undergoing combined Holmium laser enucleation of prostate (HoLEP) and hernioplasty with mesh (group B) at an academic center and compared to control group of 107 patients with HoLEP alone (group A) and found that Group B has as significant longer operative time. The mean operative time in our study was 3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes. Length of stay and duration of catheter was comparable among groups. In our study the mean hospital stay was 3.5 ± 1.0 days and mean duration of duration of folleys catheterization was 50.9 ± 15.9 hr. Ultimately combined approach was not associated to a higher complication rate. Few patients had co-morbid conditions such as hypertension ($N = 12$), ischaemic heart disease ($N = 2$), diabetes mellitus ($N = 8$), hypothyroidism ($N = 3$) and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease ($N = 2$). In our study 17 (17.9%), 37 (38.9%), 9 (9.5%), 4 (4.2%) and 3(3.2%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension, CAD, Asthma/COPD and CKD, respectively.

In a retrospective study by Harvitkar et al [15] who studied the concurrent laparoscopic totally extraperitoneal hernia repair (TEP) and transurethral resection of prostate (TURP) done on 17 patients and found that the mean age was 65 yrs, 2 had IHD, 8 had DM, 3 had hypothyroidism, 2 had COPD, 9(52.9%) had bilateral hernia, 8(47% with 5 right sided and 3 left sided) had unilateral hernia, 4(23.5%) had recurrent hernia, the mean operation time was 115min and mean post operative stay was 3.7 days. 2 patients with unilateral TEP developed seroma, two patients with bilateral TEP developed seroma, none had significant post operative bleeding or hematoma or mesh infection, only 1 patient had minor intraoperative optic trochar site bleeding which was easily controlled and 2(11.7%) developed post TURP urethral stricture. Similar findings were there in our study. In our study out of 95 patients who underwent inguinal hernioplasty and TURP in a single sitting mean age was 72.05 ± 6.36 yrs which is on higher side and 17 (17.9%), 37 (38.9%), 9 (9.5%), 4 (4.2%) and 3(3.2%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension, CAD, Asthma/COPD and CKD respectively. In this study 67 (70.5%) had unilateral hernia [26(27.4%) left and 41(43.2%) right sided] and 28(29.5%) had bilateral hernia. In this study 8(8.4%) patients had earlier history of same side hernioplasty and 9 (9.5%) had contralateral side hernioplasty. Only 8(8.4%) patients had recurrent hernia. In this study

the meantime taken for the combined surgery was 3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes and average duration of hospital stay was 3.5 ± 1.0 days. Post operation no patients developed port site hemorrhage or infection and even no gross hematuria was developed. Only 2(2.1%) patients developed mild hemorrhage which was managed immediately and 1(1.1%) developed spermatic cord injury which was repaired in the same sitting. The different findings were due to different sample size.

A systemic review and meta-analysis study by Cornu et al [16] who evaluated the efficacy and safety of transurethral ablative procedures for BPO and found bipolar transurethral resection of the prostate (B-TURP) and monopolar transurethral resection of the prostate (M-TURP) were not significantly different in terms of in terms of short-term efficacy though perioperative complications were lesser with B-TURP. Compared with M-TURP holmium laser enucleation of the prostate (HoLEP) had better short-term efficacy outcomes, fewer immediate complications, and a shorter hospital stay. Even Green Light photo selective vaporization of the prostate (PVP) was associated with a shorter hospital stay and fewer complications when compared with M-TURP did not reveal no short-term efficacy outcome difference. In our study among the 9 patients who underwent Bipolar TURP, 2 (22.2%) developed intra-operative complications and among 86 patients who underwent laser prostatectomy, 1(1.2%) patient developed post-operative complications, and this difference was statistically significant. (0.023). So, in our study too the laser prostatectomy was better surgery for TURP in respect of complications compared to bipolar TURP (B-TURP).

In a retrospective study by Hsu et al [17] in Chi Medical Centre which included 85 patients of combined surgery of TURP and hernioplasty the mean age of the study subject was 71.1 ± 7.8 years with 30 patients had a direct type inguinal hernia, 40 had an indirect type, and 15 had mixed hernia. In our study too the mean age was 72.05 ± 6.36 yrs and 40(42.1%) had direct hernia, 34(35.8%) had indirect hernia and rest 21(22.1%) had mixed hernia. Hsu et al reported 62 patients had unilateral and 23 had bilateral hernias and 12 had history of recurrent hernia with 6 having on same side and 6 on different side. In our study 67(70.5%) had unilateral hernia and rest 28 (29.5%) had bilateral hernia. In this study 8(8.4%) patients had earlier history of same side hernioplasty and 9 (9.5%) had contralateral side hernioplasty. Hsu et al reported that the mean prostate volume was 60.3 ± 26.5 ml which in our study was 60.5 ± 16.2 ml. The mean surgical time was 3 h and 31 min \pm 65 min which in our study was 3hr 31 minutes \pm 53 minutes. The mean resected

prostate was 19.5 ± 16.2 g which in our study was 31.3 ± 6.8 ml. No patient experienced significant intraoperative complications but in our study 2(2.1%) patients developed mild hemorrhage which was managed immediately and 1(1.1%) developed spermatic cord injury which was repaired in the same sitting. The mean catheter retention time was 51.6 ± 16.7 hr which in our study was 50.9 ± 15.9 hr. The mean postoperative hospital stay was 2.9 ± 1.0 days which in our study was 3.5 ± 1.0 days.

A significant difference was noted in operative times between open hernioplasty (3 h 45 min \pm 67 min) and laparoscopic hernioplasty (LH) (2 h 55 min \pm 45 min) ($p < 0.05$) which in our study was 3hr50min \pm 53min and 3hr \pm 36min respectively and that too significantly different ($p < 0.05$). That means LH took lesser time to operate compared to open hernioplasty in both studies. The mean Foleys catheter retention for open and lap hernioplasty was 54.5 ± 17.9 h and 44.7 ± 11 h ($p < 0.05$) which in our study was 56.26 ± 15.33 hr and 42.65 ± 13.19 hr respectively and that too statistically significantly different ($p < 0.05$). That also means in both studies the Foleys catheter retention time was significantly lesser in laparoscopic hernioplasty compared to open hernioplasty signifying the efficacy of former over later.

Conclusion

Transurethral resection of prostate and concomitant inguinal hernioplasty has a better outcome and reduced patient morbidity. There were few intra-operative complications like hemorrhage and spermatic cord injury, lesser mean operation time, lesser catheterization time, lesser recatheterization, lesser use of analgesic and antibiotics and none post operative stay complications. Compared to open hernioplasty, laparoscopic hernioplasty when done with TURP had lesser mean operative time, duration of stay, lesser duration of Folley's catheterization, lesser analgesic, and antibiotic use. So along with most other studies this study emphasized that it is better to do inguinal hernioplasty and trans urethral resection of prostate in a single sitting as total duration of hospital stay, total duration of catheterization, antibiotic use, analgesic use etc lesser and even number of complications are either same or lesser when compared to doing both operation in different sittings.

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